

Limits of Parliamentary Oversight- A Practical Study of the UAE's Constitution

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Abstract

Studying the limits of the parliamentary oversight is marked by a great importance in defining the oversight role the assemblies' practice over the works of the executive authority, through constitutional and legal means organizing these means; in order to provide full opportunity to the oversight role. To define these limits; we have to identify the concept of the parliamentary oversight, their means according to the orientations of the constitutions, and the extent to which the assemblies are bound by these limits to achieve the intended purpose.

Introduction

It is well known that the elected assemblies are considered as the fundamental pillar of democracy; whereas, people are practicing their direct political role via electing their representatives to speak out their demands, ideas, and opinions on various issues therefore, democracy can not be achieved without the elected assemblies resemble the will of the people, and work on fulfilling their interests and aspirations; thus, it is described as the effective mean in the state that works on enacting the legal enactments, in addition to its oversight role on the works of the executive authority. Regards to the oversight role practiced by these assemblies, which work via it to ensure and verify the performance of the executive authority, implementing the legal provisions properly and in conformity with the provisions of the constitution, via questioning the state's ministries and its affiliated bodies, whether this questioning was in the form of questions and questioning, parliamentary investigations, or via adopting no-confidence, and forcing the cabinet to resign. The parliamentary oversight gets impacted by the current political system, as it is considered as the core of the political oversight on the works of the executive authority, and so this role differs according to the difference in the pattern of the relationship between the two authorities; within the democratic parliamentary systems the parliamentary oversight is practiced on a larger scale than the presidential systems, and because of the importance of this role as it informs the citizen mainly about the works of the executive authority via the constitutional means available to the assembly.

Consequently, our study for this research shall be divided into four themes as follows:

The First Theme: The Concept of the Parliamentary Oversight

The Second Theme: The Limits of the Parliamentary Oversight

The Third Theme: The Means of the Parliamentary Oversight

The Fourth Theme: The Emirati Constitution application for the Parliamentary Oversight.

The First Theme: The Concept of the Parliamentary Oversight

Generally, and linguistically, oversight is defined as; "Evaluating works as a prelude to what they truly are" while, in terms of the terminological meaning; the constitutional experts were not interested in setting a definition to it, even though it is one of the oldest parliamentary duties, which in turn reflected on the lack of the definitions that were set by the researchers for the constitutional jurisprudence. Initially, it was defined by Researcher Pierre as; "One of the oldest duties of the parliaments; and its goal is to set limits before the executive authority", also Jurist Harris defined it as; "The process of examining laws after their enactment, to demonstrate the extent of their implementation if it achieved the desired results. And what are the procedures to be taken to correct the mistakes in this concern?" However, Prof. Fares Omran has defined it as; "Fact-finding about the government works by the legislative authority", to detect the failure in the proper implementation of the general rules in the state, and identify the responsible and held him accountable."

Despite the fact that jurists have disagreed in their definition to the oversight; this disagreement is not considered a fundamental disagreement affects the process of oversight or its substance; as their disagreement

were about defining the main goal of the parliamentary oversight which is detecting the improper implementation of the general rules in the state, and identify the one who is responsible about it, and held him politically accountable.

Based upon the aforementioned; parliamentary oversight is one of the forms of political oversight, which is practiced exclusively by the MPs of the legislative authority over the members of the executive authority. Consequently, this explains to us that the parliamentary oversight includes two parties; the first party is the parliament MP who practices the oversight, and the second party who is the one subject to the oversight; the member of the executive authority.

As long as it is all related to the fundamental powers of the state, the process of oversight itself is affected by the nature of the political system, and the system of the government (Parliamentary, Presidential), as the democratic systems that depend on a multi-party basis, give the MP the full freedom to express his right in the cabinet or practicing his oversight role, but in fact, this freedom is clear only in the theoretical field, as the practical application of this right could get the political process into a political impasse, or it may cause problems to the MP who practices his oversight role if he was affiliated to the ruling party especially, in the countries where there is a consistency between the MP and his party like in Britain; where no MP could vote against his party.

While in the systems based upon the sole political organization, whereas one party dominates, or whereas the dominant party, here the parliamentary oversight is of no use, as all MPs or the majority of them are committed to the dominant party, which reflects heavily on the oversight. However, the citizen's political knowledge on a general scale; and the MP's on a special scale, may have a major role in getting over the partisan influences, and political manipulation, since some party-based cliques may have an effective impact on the performance of the government.

In regards to the system of governance, the means that the MP have in the parliamentary system are more extensive than those available for the MP within the presidential system, since the parliamentary system is based on the concept of cooperation and balance between the legislative and executive authorities consequently, each authority has oversight means over the other. The legislative authority has the right of voting non-confidence in ministers, the right of exerting oversight over the works of the ministers via the available means of oversight, either via (question, questioning and investigation, and discussing the subject, however, the executive authority has the right to dissolve the legislature authority prior to the expiration date).

Whilst in the presidential system, it depends on the concept of the separation between the powers, the legislative authority functions independently without the minimum participation by the executive authority similarly, the executive authority functions independently without the minimum participation by any other authority, whereas the executive authority is concentrated within the Head of the State who has the powers to appoint, oust and eliminate the ministers from their positions if, it was proved that they have committed an action violates the policy the president set and ordered. Thus, there is no relation with the parliament, who has no right to hold them accountable for their deeds, whether via question and questioning, or via the general policy reports as in the parliamentary system, as in this system the ministers are in charge of the general policy. That is in theory; however, the practical application knew some sort of cooperation between the two authorities, as in the United States of America; where the concept of the separation between powers is no longer based on rigid segregation but, it allowed a flexible separation and the cooperation within the authorities as well. It also allowed an oversight for the authorities over each other, as it gave the congress the authority to form committees to investigate the works of the executive authority; and probably the basis for this was not a constitutional provision but; it was driven from the judgments handed down by the American Judiciary, to enlarge the powers of the congress to form committees in all fields; political, economic and social, and set only one restriction over this practice which is; not using this practice as a mean in itself, but using it to find the truth.

The Second Theme: The Limits of the Parliamentary Oversight

It is already agreed upon that, the parliamentary oversight is making the executive authority practices its duties within the frame of the constitution and the law; for the common good of the citizens, and this is the essence of the idea of oversight, where the MPs practice oversight generally over the works of the authority, and the power of this oversight extends to include the various organizations in the state, and it takes the form of questioning and approving the policies of the government prior to its execution like, approving the budget draft, and expressing the opinion about the general policy of the state.

The limits of the parliamentary oversight are extensive; it includes all the activities and works of the executive authority, to ensure its commitment to the principle of legitimacy, and making all its actions subject to the constitution and the applicable laws. However, the oversight mainly concentrates on the fundamental issues and the general matters, and stays away from the partial details, probably, this might be due to the large volume of the administrative works required to be oversighted, in addition to the shortness of the term of the parliamentary session, which does not allow the legislative authority enough time to review the subtlest and

partial things, consequently, it satisfies itself with oversight the fundamental general policy only, and leaves ending the partial things to the other oversight bodies, whether the administrative or financial one.

The general origin of oversight in its concept is; verifying and ensuring, which means examining it before and after the operation, in regard to the parliamentary oversight; it could include those who are involved so, it could be preceding and subsequent at the same time. Hence, the MP can question the minister about the policies of the ministry, or about a certain incident that happened, or even about the works and matters finished before his term, which in this matter includes the concept of the subsequent oversight, he could also be subject to question, questioning and even no-confidence, based upon the available means to the MP under the constitution. It could also include in meaning, the preceding oversight; by adopting the budget plan, defining its general framework, and determining the disclosure of the plan application, and these are within the matters that include in its meaning; the preceding oversight.

Nevertheless, the practical application, and the difficulty of the awareness- as we mentioned earlier- of the overall actions of the government, made the parliamentary oversight looks as it was a subsequent oversight to fulfill its intended purpose accordingly, the exact meaning of oversight is; the verifying and the detection of the error, and not blocking the flow of the governmental work, subsequently, we do not believe that there is any harm if an MP found out that there is a ministry doing something that is violating the law or the constitution, and therefore, the MP shall have the right to question this matter, provided that he enforces his questioning by the supporting evidence.

The Third Theme: The Means of the Parliamentary Oversight

The parliamentary oversight over the works of the executive authority needs procedures that are stipulated in the constitution; as it's the supreme document in the state that regulates all the state's authorities and defines its competencies and the means of its practice. Constitutions usually provide for such means directly and explicitly and leave the detailed matters that organize the operation of oversight itself to the domestic laws and regulations. In most cases, the domestic system of the legislative authority includes this kind of matter, hence, Article 85, of the Emirati Constitution of 1971 stipulated that: "The Council shall have a Secretariat, to be chaired by a Secretary-General, the domestic regulation shall define its competencies, the Council shall be the one in charge of setting its domestic regulation, and it shall be issued under a resolution by the President of the Federation and subject to the approval of the Federal Supreme Council." While, Article 65, of the Iraqi Constitution of 2005, stipulated that: A legislative Council called "The Federation Council" shall be established, includes representatives of the provinces and the governorates which are not part of a region, and it shall regulate its composition and conditions of membership." Likewise; Article 101, of the Egyptian Constitution of 2014, which stipulated: "The Parliament shall have the right to legislate, approving the general policy of the State, the overall economic and social plan, and the State's general budget, and it shall also has the right to oversight the works of the executive authority, all of this are included in the constitution."

If the ministerial responsibility is the base for oversight, as the executive authority is responsible before the parliament, then the adopted means for the oversight vary in degree and strength subject to the difference in situations and circumstances which define this responsibility. Accordingly, there are indirect means embody the responsibility like; "questions, requests for discussion, and investigation committees), and direct means to confirm the responsibility like; "questioning, and no confidence).

Nevertheless, some didn't give importance to this distribution according to the responsibility, instead affirmed including it under the heading means of the parliamentary oversight, and divided it into three sections: the oversight over the parliamentary authority; the MP practices it under his constitutional powers, and it includes impeachment, information oversight; and its embodied in means where the MP gathers information or wants to draw the government attention to important information such as (the request for briefing or question), and confront oversight, whereas, the MPs feel the responsibility towards the society to safeguard its interests and confront the government or try to repair the general policies like; (hearings, and commissions of inquiry).

These means were divided into main means like (question, questioning, parliamentary investigation, and the requests of general discussions, any other mean isn't more than a mean to inform the government like; the requests for briefing, petitions, and suggestions of will or decision) or an intense oversight results like in no confidence or renewing it (it could also be completely out of the properly parliamentary oversight field like accusing the ministers criminally).

Whatever the previous divisions were, we think that the ministerial responsibility is the base of the oversight, and as long as there is responsibility, there is a mean to accountability. Therefore, this means diverse and include: question, raising a general topic to discussion, parliamentary investigation, questioning, and no-confidence.

Question:

Question refers to the right of any MP to question the prime minister or any minister, with to obtain information about something he doesn't know, finding out what the government intends to do in a special matter, or what is included within the ministry's activities which headed by this minister. Consequently, question is considered one of the rights of the MPs, that is asked to the prime minister, ministers, deputy

ministers, or other executive officials of the government, concerning any matter within their competence. Accordingly, the answers for these questions shall be verbal during the session, unless it were asked in writing, or the questioner required that the answer should be in writing. Most of the parliamentary systems require that the questions should be asked by one MP only, and to be concerning a general matter within the competencies of the official.

Setting a General Topic for Discussion:

It is a constitutional right for a number of MPs, to set a general topic about the domestic or the foreign policy before the legislative chamber; with the purpose of modifying the course of the government's policy and especially, the performance of the executive authority.

This right aims to the free discussion that leads to exchanging views, with intention of finding a solution approved by all the involved parties. Any MP could take part in this discussion, indifferent to what happens in asking question, which creates a special relationship between the questioner and the minister who was asked.

Generally, the discussion ends with, a resolution that includes the opinion of the parliament in the subject matter, or the close of the discussion and moving to the agenda.

On this point, it's worth mention that, the government in addition to the parliament, shall benefit from this by knowing the directions of the parliament about the subject matter, and the extent to which it supports its policy.

Parliamentary Investigation:

Parliamentary investigation refers to a method of investigation organized by the legislative authority to oversight the government, or it is a procedure taken by the parliament with the intention of informing, and based upon it, the parliament can decide its position.

Some constitutions granted the MPs the right to form special committees within themselves to hold investigations about a special matter, and also the right to ask all the different ministries and bodies to prepare what is needed of documents or data to be able to investigate the truth, and monitoring the function of the executive process, in conformity with the constitutional and legal provisions.

These investigation committees also have a significant role, along with the other means, in the oversight over the executive authority. Nonetheless, its oversight role is restricted to a specific subject, so it doesn't have the right to exceed the assembly's oversight powers. Moreover, its competence is restricted to submitting a report to the assembly, and unveiling the truth, consequently, its report doesn't entail the accountability of the Ministry.

Questioning:

It's the right of the MP to demand the government or, the competent minister to provide information about the state's policy, any subject concerning the works of the executive authority, or even to ask the minister to appear before the legislative assembly to clarify the subject matter. Therefore, some call this kind of questioning, the accountability and criticism of the government's actions, as it carries the meaning of accusation by the parliament against the prime minister or one of his ministers with the intention of revealing the integrity of the minister's act in the matter subject of his accountability, consequently, it may end up with raising the matter of the political responsibility of the cabinet and voting on confidence on the cabinet or the competent minister.

Questioning is conditioned to be constitutionally based on specific facts and subjects and to include a brief and general statement about the facts to ensure the seriousness of its intended goals, and being away of personal objects and political goals that plan to oust a specific Ministry

The motion of Confidence:

It is the procedure that allows the parliament to vote no confidence on one of the ministers or all of the cabinet if the performance of that minister or the cabinet requires accountability, and it entails the minister's or the cabinet's resignation.

Accordingly, ministerial responsibility is considered one of the most serious forms of the parliamentary oversight over the government. It shows up in two forms: it could be an individual responsibility of one of the ministers or a group of specified ministers, naturally, this happens only in the cases where the minister is free to act by himself, therefore, the minister takes personally the full responsibility of his mistakes, consequently, the inevitable result for the no-confidence voting is the resignation of the minister or ministries who were subject to the no-confidence voting. While, the other form of the political responsibility is the joint responsibility; which means the responsibility of the cabinet as a whole, and this is in the event that the general policy of the government was inappropriate to the state interest from the parliament point of view, or because of the prime minister's responsibility, if it was approved that it is the joint responsibility of the ministers; then all the cabinet ministers shall be obligated to resign under the principle of solidarity on which the parliamentary system is based on

The Fourth Theme: The UAE Constitution application for the Parliamentary Oversight.

The UAE Constitution of 1971, stipulated the means of the oversight of the National Council, through these means, the Council shall practice its oversight role, to clarify the way in which the governmental workflows,

those means shall be identified subject to the constitutional stipulations, the provisions of the domestic regulation of the Federal National Council, as follows

1- Setting General subject for discussion

Article 92 of the constitution stipulated on this mean; (the Federal National Council shall have the right to discuss any of the general subjects of the Federal, unless the Council of Ministry informed the Federal National Council that discussing this subject is against the highest interests of the Federal, subsequently, the Prime Minister or the competent minister shall appear in the discussion. The Federal National Council shall have the right to express its recommendations and identifies the subjects to be discussed, hence, if the Council of Ministry did not approve these recommendations, it shall inform the Federal National Council of the reasons for the non-approving.)

The domestic regulation of the Federal National Council had set the procedures for setting a subject for discussion, in details, whereas Article 103 stated that (subject to a request signed by 5 members; a general subject about the Federal's affairs may be set to be discussed by the Council to clarify the government's policy in it, and to exchange views. Hence, all Council's members shall have the right to participate in the discussion, accordingly, the Council may make recommendations in this subject).

The regulation had also given the government the right to practice this right by itself, and this was stipulated in Article 111; the government may, by itself or under a question addressed to it, request to discuss a specific subject related to the affairs of the Federal to get the recommendation of the Federal, or to make statements about it.

Subsequently, the regulation added in Article 104: (the President of the Council shall be informed about any request once the request is submitted to the Prime Minister. The Federal National Council may list the request in the agenda of the first meeting held fifteen days of the following date of notifying the Council of Ministers of the request. If the Council of Ministers objected to the discussion of the subject due to considerations related to the supreme interests of the Federal; the subject shall be eliminated from the agenda, or the Council may have the right to view the subject, or referring it to one of the committees for consideration and submitting a report about it before taking the final decision)

The regulation also, authorized the right to accept the right to waiver the request for discussion subject to Article 105, (if the applicants abdicated the request or missed the session set for consideration; five members may adopt the request, consequently, the Council may continue to consider the request, or eliminate it from the agenda).

Based upon the aforementioned; the Federal National Council practices via this mean an oversight authority, this authority could be precedent, and could be subsequent to asking questions to the members of the government.

2- Asking question to the members of the Council of Ministers

The questions asked by the members of the Federal National Council to the members of the Council of Ministers of the Federal Cabinet, are considered as a kind of oversight practiced by the member of the Federal National Council, via which, the questioning and clarification are done with the intention of getting information or statements related to the governmental work, or any subject under the scope of its works; with the purpose of identifying these works, therefore, Article 93 stipulated that; (the Federal's government shall be represented in the sessions of the Federal National Council by the Prime Minister, one of his deputies, or one of the ministers competent to the questions made by any member of the Federal National Council, to inquire the matters within their competences, pursuant to the procedures set in the domestic regulation of the Council.

Based upon the aforementioned text; the regulation has organized who is the body that have the right to ask questions, and the specific conditions for asking questions, as follows:

A) The right to asking questions:

Article 116 of the Domestic Regulation of the Federal National Council stipulated that "Each member shall have the right to ask the Prime Minister and the ministers, to inquire about the matters within their competences, including the inquiry about a matter the member does not know, and investigating an incident happened and the member heard about it. The question may be asked by one member, and the question shall be addressed either to the Prime Minister or to one minister only".

B) The body that was asked the question:

- Article 118 of the Domestic Regulation of the Federal National Council stipulated that "pursuant to the aforementioned article, the President of the Council shall inform the Prime Minister or the competent minister about the question, then the question shall be listed in the agenda of the first session held after the date of informing the Prime Minister or the competent minister, the regulation also granted the Prime Minister or the competent minister the right to postpone the answer subject to Article 119 which stipulated that "the Prime Minister or the competent minister shall reply to the question in the session set for its consideration, the Prime Minister or the competent minister may have the right to ask for postponing the answer to no more than two weeks, consequently this request shall be approved, hence, the postponing shall not be to more than this period unless it was subject to the Council decision. The

Prime Minister or the competent minister may have the right to upon the questioner approval or in his absence- submit the answers or the required statements in the General Secretariat of the Council for the information of the members, and he shall record this submitting in the session's minute"

Conditions for the question's validity:

Articles 110 to 115 have organized the conditions for the question's validity as follows:

The questioner- no other members- shall have the right to comment on the answer, this comment shall be for two times and in brief, it shall also be in accordance with the affairs of the Federal, in order to grant the Council's recommendations or statements in this concern.

- The regulation granted the government the right; that the government may, on its own or subject to a question addressed to it, demand to discuss a specific subject, provided that,
- The preceding procedures of the questions shall not be applied on what is addressed to the Prime Minister or the ministers during the discussion of the budget, or any other subject on the Council's agenda, however, the members shall have the right to address these questions in the session verbally.
- It also granted, if the questioner revoked his question, the right of any other member to adopt the question, in this case, the Council shall continue discussing the question, or else the question shall be set aside.
- Answering the questions addressed to the Prime Minister or the ministers within the regular meetings shall be in writing and addressed to the President of the Council, who is ,in turn, shall send it to the members asked it, therefore, these answers to those questions shall not be restricted with the dates prescribed in the aforementioned articles, and it shall be listed on the agenda of the Council's next session.
- The questions shall expire by the end of the questioner term for any reason, unless another member of the Council adopts the question, in this case, the Council shall continue the discussion.

3- Considering the claims submitted to the Council:

The UAE Constitution pursued the concept stipulates that the rights and liberties shall not be violated, according to Article 141 thereof, which stipulated; "Every person shall submit the claim to the competent authorities, including the judicial authorities, about any violation to the rights and liberties contained herein"

Based upon the above Article; the constitutional legislator mentioned submitting the claims to the judicial authorities, and the competent authorities but; without identifying those authorities, accordingly; the domestic regulation of the National Council came in line with the constitution's stipulation and allowed submitting the claims to the National Council, under Article 116, "the claims submitted to the Council shall be signed by its provider, and mentioned in it; the name, address, and profession of its provider. The President of the Council is entitled to archive the claims submitted to the Council, in contrary to the terms of the previous period, while; Articles 117- 121 have identified the conditions for submitting a claim, as follows:

- Article 117; the claims submitted to the Council shall be registered in a special record, with serial numbers subject to the date of its submitting, with the name, address, and brief about its subject.
- Article 118; the President of the Council is entitled to ask the Prime Minister, or the competent ministers to provide the statements and clarifications concerning the claim. Consequently; the one who was addressed with the request shall submit the required clarifications in no more than three weeks of the referral date.
- Article 119; the President of the Council shall refer all the claims to the claims committee, along with the answers received from the competent ministries.
- Article 120; the committee shall consider the claims referred to it, and it shall have the right to ask the competent ministry to provide any additional statements or data it sees needed to consider the claim.
- Article 121; the committee shall inform the claim provider, via the President of the Council, of the result of the claim consideration. If the committee thought that the subject of the claim and the reply of the ministry constitutes a matter that the Council should have an opinion in, the committee shall have to submit a report in this concern to the Council.

Conclusion:

- 1- The proper application of the parliamentary oversight means in any political system, has to be established in a democratic atmosphere governed by understanding, in order to get the most out of it, as the main purpose of the oversight is not distorting, putting obstacles in the way of the political action, or ousting a specific minister, but it is to make sure that the constitutional and legislative norms are applied properly in the country.
- 2- The need for cooperation between the executive authority and the House of Representatives, along with providing the required information, as the executive authority is the source of information. Whenever the dealing was smooth and easy, it will reflect on the oversight performance.
- 3- The contribution in developing the proficiency of the MPs via organizing courses and seminars on oversight work, informing them about the oversight practices of the Arab and Western parliaments, and

drawing on their experiences, opening up to the research centers, consulting firms, and creating joint cooperation.

- 4- Enhancing the oversight role of the civil society institutions, and take advantage of their reports, provided that these reports are based on real information.
- 5- The UAE Constitution selected the right path by adopting the way of submitting claims directly to the National Council, and this, in turn, enhances and strengthens the democratic notions.

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